

Implementing gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe

D7.1 Dissemination and Communication strategy

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¹ PU= Public, CO=Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services), CL=Classified, as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

GA	Grant Agreement
RPO	Research Performance Organization
RFO	Research Funding Organization
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
WP	Work package
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
AT	Athena Project
C&D	Communication and Dissemination

Executive Summary

The current document is a report on Deliverable 7.1 “Dissemination and Communication strategy” (M3); from Workpackage WP7 “Communication and Dissemination” of the ATHENA project (GA nº 101006416). This report is a concise plan to guide the communication and dissemination activities of the ATHENA project. The tools, procedures and guidelines to be adopted by partners are defined to ensure a clear, constant and coherent communication and dissemination of the project results to the desired target audiences.

The D7.1 report intends to be a starting point to integrate the perspectives of organizations with different purposes, backgrounds and visions with the same goal of removing barriers to the recruitment, retention and career progression of female researchers; address gender imbalances in decision making processes; generate a cultural change needed to avoid future gender bias and discriminatory practices. The implementation of the GEPs will generate a sustainable cultural and institutional change that in turns will allow to unlock the research potential of the partnering organizations.

The project focuses on 8 research organisations and universities and research funding organizations of selected EU Central-Eastern countries and outermost regions, which appear to be lagging behind EU trend with respect to the goals.

The “Communication & Dissemination Strategy” is a document that will evolve and develop during the project’s life cycle, in order to respond to the partners’ needs if necessary taking in to account the changes agreed by the consortium partners and following the GA commitments. The FRCT team will be responsible to define and implement the Communication & Dissemination Strategy and will require the contribution of all partners, namely to define basic communication aims, as the following:

- **Which target groups we need to reach per deliverable?**
- **Which target groups we want to reach for ATHENA Dissemination & Communication activities (workshops, webinars, etc.)?**
- **With which kind of message we want to convey?**
- **In which timeframe?**
- **With what kind of tools?**

The production of communication tools will reply to the following questions, to be addressed by the project partners:

- Who has to be involved in order to create these tools?
- What kind of information needs to be available to create the tools?
- How, where, when and by whom this shall be distributed to the respective target groups?

In addition, a project website, maintained along and beyond the project, will be developed at the beginning, presenting the objectives of the project as well as the participants profile part of the consortium.

The main purpose of the communication strategy is to maximise the impact of the findings and conclusions of the project and raise awareness about the state of gender equality in the project organizations and country, and present the reality of women in the context of the RPO's and RFO's. This strategy will be fully aligned with the general objective of the project, of creating and implementing Gender Equality Plans through sustainable, comprehensive and innovative means.

1 CONTEXT ANALYSIS

1.1 The Project

The Athena project is dedicated to contribute to the objectives set by the EU in the Europe 2020, growth strategy and achieve smart and sustainable growth gender equality, as it aims at supporting Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) and Research Funding Organisations (RFOs) in developing and implementing Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) as a way to generate systemic institutional change.

One of the main objectives of Europe's societies is the elimination of all types of discrimination associated with gender. Therefore the Athena's project is aligned with the idea that the fundamental human right must be included at the core of political debate in Europe and actions must be taken to overcome the existing and persistent gender gap in Europe.

The equality between women and men is a fundamental value of the European Union, as vital to its economic and social development and it's in the core of Athena's context and goals. Athena's project contributes to reply to equality gap by removing barriers to recruitment and career progression of female researchers, include and strengthen the gender dimension in research programmes and address gender imbalances in decision-making, as well as promoting the implementation of GEPs by reaching the support of the highest management level of the organisations.

Although there is positive signs of change, as the annual report on equality between women and men from the European Commission pointed, as the employment rates have reached historically high levels in the EU and more women than ever are in positions of power. These are only signs of hope as the big steps remain to be done for gender equality, as we still have high number of highly skilled female graduates, and very few of them embrace a research career. With almost 60% of women graduates in EU, only one third of the EU's researchers are women.

Taking in to account the current state of the art in Europe, ATHENA's project has the objective of removing barriers to the recruitment, retention and career progression of female researchers; address gender imbalances in decision making processes and generate a cultural change needed to avoid future gender bias and discriminatory practices. To do so the project actions aim at creating and implementing of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) in 6 Research Performing and 2 Research Funding organisations.

To ensure systemic institutional change, ATHENA will first conduct an assessment of procedures and practices already in place in partner RPOs and RFOs, together with an

analysis of the national legislation and policy frameworks. In parallel, it will put in place a participatory process aimed, on one side, to understand the needs and the preferences of the stakeholders and, on the other side, to train them with regard to selected topics related to gender. Based on these two approaches GEPs will be drafted, implemented and monitored in each partner organisation. All of these actions will be supported by a communication strategy that will not only disseminate the results of the project work as it will communicate to a wider audience, as well as target stakeholders, in order to raise awareness, support and understanding of the issue and by doing so Athena project intend to have a replicative effect.

1.2 The Consortium

The Athena's partner organisations belong to Central Eastern EU countries and EU Outermost regions that show some of the lowest Gender Equality Indexes in the EU. Thanks to the implementation of the GEPs, ATHENA will contribute to unlocking the research potential of these organisations thus improving the overall performance of the European Research Area and helping to close the innovation divide by avoiding the waste of talent and inefficient use of skilled women from weaker regions of the EU.

The ATHENA project is coordinated by Consulta Europa (CE) and it has a consortium of 10 partners from 8 different countries, ranging from universities and research institutes to private company and public organizations that are some way engaged with research and science and have interest in Framework Programs and European financing overall. The project partners are the following:

1. **CE-Consulta Europa Projects Projects and Innovation (Canary Islands, Spain)**
2. **JSI – Institut Jozef Stefan (Slovenia)**
3. **Uniwersytet Jana Kochanowskiego W Kielcach (Poland)**
4. **Universitatea Din Bucuresti (Romania)**
5. **ULPGC – Universidad De Las Palmas De Gran Canaria (Canary Islands, Spain)**
6. **IRPPS – Consiglio Nazionale Delle Ricerche (Italy)**
7. **Ustav Vyskumu Socialnej Komunikacie Slovenskej Akademie Vied (Slovakia)**
8. **University Of Ruse Angel Kanchev (Bulgaria)**
9. **GOBCAN – Gobierno De Canarias (Canary Islands, Spain)**
10. **FRCT – Fundo Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia (Azores, Portugal)**

1.3 ATHENA Dissemination and Communication - Workpackage 7

The WP7 is dedicated to communicate the project, as well as disseminate the outcomes and the results obtained within the project, by engaging a wider audience, at the several levels of stakeholders of audience target for this project. Through dissemination activities, the project aims also at creating a strong network that will ensure the sustainability and impact of the project itself, to support the emergence of a fertile community. Raise awareness, as well as inform and serve as an example for the required Gender Plan to the RPO's and RFO's, in order to align them with the new mandatory requirements of the Horizon Europe² and European Union (EU) targets when it comes to the wider implementation of equality plan for the EU.

During the whole duration of the project, this Workpackage will be aiming at enhancing the exploitation and replicability of project outcomes. WP7 leader will define together with the other partners a dissemination and communication plan to be executed for the whole duration of the project. Several outcomes are expected from this WP, and in particular: project website, promotional material and visual identity, newsletters, organisation and attendance of dissemination events such as conferences, seminars, workshops and/or other events organised by similar EU funded projects at national and EU level, organisation of a final project conference in Brussels presenting project results.

The WP7, as the Athena's Workpackage dedicated to communication and dissemination, will be devoted to disseminating the results of the project and to create a communication plan for fostering the visibility of the project itself.

The dissemination and exploitation of the results achieved throughout the project will strengthen the overall impact of project activities. The dissemination strategy will make use of a broad range of tailored tools and actions in order to achieve the following objectives:

- ✓ **Raise awareness of the project activities and results;**
- ✓ **Disseminate information among relevant stakeholders, in particular RPOs, including Higher Education Institutions, and RFOs and also public authorities in charge of education, research and work policies;**

² Integration of the gender dimension into research and innovation content (i.e. sex and gender analysis) becomes a requirement by default across the whole programme (https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/research_and_innovation/strategy_on_research_and_innovation/documents/ec_rtd_gender-equality-factsheet.pdf)

- ✓ **Increase the number of RPOs and RFOs taking up GEPs, addressing gender imbalances and strengthening gender dimension at their organisational level;**
- ✓ **Facilitate the internal and external communication of project partners.**

Furthermore, project deliverables will be openly accessible by organisations all over Europe with the purpose of facilitating the exploitation at EU level.

D7.1 Dissemination and Communication strategy

The Deliverable 7.1 is the first in this WP7, the starting point of this Workpackage. This deliverable is dedicated to the elaboration of a “Dissemination and Communication strategy” for the project Athena (GA101006416) that includes Task 7.1 “Development of a communication and dissemination strategy”. This first stage of the WP7 presents the answers of “when”, “where” and “how”, the identified target groups will be reached by the dissemination and communication activities and maximize the impact, as well as promote, the project activities. This is also a deliverable that will guide the roll-out of WP6, as well as it will be essential for the success of other WP’s, due to its transversal nature.

In order to contribute to the overall goal of the Athena project, the WP7 has five deliverables to be implemented along the 48 months of the project, all lead by FRCT, with the contribution of all partners, as described in image 1.

- **D7.1 Dissemination and Communication strategy (M3);**
- **D7.2 Project visual identity and website (M5);**
- **D7.3 Scientific and nonscientific Publications (M48);**
- **D7.4 Reports on participation and organisation of events - v1 (M30);**
- **D7.5 Reports on participation and organisation of events – vfinal (M48).**

Task 7.1 Development of a communication and dissemination strategy

The WP7 has previewed also six tasks that will complete and align the implementation of the deliverables:

- ✓ **Task 7.1 Development of a communication and dissemination strategy, M1-M3 (Lead Partner: FRCT; other participating partners: all partners involved);**

- ✓ **Task 7.2 Project visual identity and promotional materials, M1-M5 (Task leader: FRCT; other participating partners: all partners);**
- ✓ **Task 7.3 Project website, social media and newsletter, M4-M48 (Task leader: FRCT; other participating partners: all partners involved);**
- ✓ **Task 7.4 Open Source Scientific Publications, M6-M48 (Task leader: FRCT; other participating partners: all partners);**
- ✓ **Task 7.5 Participation and organisation of events and connection/synergies with similar initiatives, M6- M48 (Task leader: FRCT; other participating partners: all partners);**
- ✓ **Task 7.6 Final Conference, M48 (Task leader: FRCT; other participating partners: all partners).**

Image 1. Chronogram of the WP7 Tasks and deliverables during the project lifetime according to the AT GA.

2 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PRINCIPLES

The project communication and dissemination should be guided by a set of five core principles upon which the ATHENA will orient its communication and dissemination action, internally and externally:

- **Reliability:** send a message of quality of research that benefits from the design, the methodology, the analysis and the use of resources;
- **Tailored messages/easy to perceive:** ATHENA needs to be able to pass on the message with ease. Being able to reach the different kind of actors, from researcher, to students, to policy makers and society in general. It's essential that the different stakeholders with different background and objectives in mind are taken into account so that the message is inclusive and accessible to all. To achieve this, appropriate channels and key messages tailored to the needs and expectations of the various target audiences, as well as national and regional sensibilities, and expressed in appropriate language (as specialised, technical wording communication vs. simple and direct, jargon-free communication);
- **Exploit synergies:** to maximize impact and efficiency opportunities of synergies should be explored, at two levels, internally, between partners and WP's, and external, namely with external network, organizations that support and collaborate with the project, platforms that have relevant remit and with Athena's "sister" projects;
- **Gender sensitive communication:** Certain words and images we use to communicate must be considered carefully since they can perpetuate images of socially-prescribed gender roles and behaviors. ATHENA will adopt a neutral, empowering language, non-hierarchical and nonpatronizing style. The language used in the project is designed to

showcase and promote gender-sensitive communication, identify gender stereotypes and use a fair and balanced representation of women and men in communication;

- **Disruptive: As this is a project that is bringing a new perspective to the table the communication intents to be disruptive, innovative and breaking with old stigmas associated with gender in in research and science, female work and career.**

The ATHENA C&D will also contribute to promote:

- ✓ **Science literacy and science education: The activities for GEP implementation and dissemination and communication;**
- ✓ **Public engagement;**
- ✓ **Open access: participating at the H2020 pilot project on open data.**

The project publications and deliverables will be published on open access repositories and will also be publicly accessible on the project's website and social media.

2.1 EC Rights and Obligations Related to Results

To implement dissemination and exploitation activities effectively, it is important to have a good understanding of the definitions of the respective terms and concepts within the context of Horizon 2020 projects. According to article 38 of the GA, the beneficiaries must promote the action and its results, by providing targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public) in a strategic and effective manner.

This does not change the dissemination obligations in Article 29, the confidentiality obligations in Article 36 or the security obligations in Article 37, all of which still apply.

Before engaging in a communication activity expected to have a major media impact, the beneficiaries must inform the Agency (see Article 52).

Information on EU funding — Obligation and right to use the EU emblem

Unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any communication activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social

media, etc.) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must:

(a) display the EU emblem

(b) include the following text for communication activities:

“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006416”.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. For the purposes of their obligations³, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Agency. This does not, however, give the partners right to exclusive use. Moreover, partners may not appropriate the EU emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

Disclaimer excluding Agency and Commission responsibility

Any communication activity related to the action must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Agency and the Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

The Agency and the Commission has the right to use the outcomes of the project, in the form of material, documents and information’s, for its communication and publicising activities, information relating to the action, documents notably summaries for publication and public deliverables as well as any other material, such as pictures or audio-visual material received from any partner of Athena project (including in electronic form).⁴

If the Agency’s or the Commission’s use of these materials, documents or information would risk compromising legitimate interests, the beneficiary concerned may request the Agency or the Commission not to use it⁵.

The right to use Athena’s materials, documents and information includes:

³ Grant agreement No 101006416, Article 38, Promoting the action — visibility of EU funding

⁴ This does not change the confidentiality obligations in Article 36 and the security obligations in Article 37, all of which still apply.

⁵ See Article 52

(a) use for its own purposes (in particular, making them available to persons working for the Agency, the Commission or any other EU institution, body, office or agency or body or institutions in EU Member States; and copying or reproducing them in whole or in part, in unlimited numbers);

(b) distribution to the public (in particular, publication as hard copies and in electronic or digital format, publication on the internet, as a downloadable or non-downloadable file, broadcasting by any channel, public display or presentation, communicating through press information services, or inclusion in widely accessible databases or indexes);

(c) editing or redrafting for communication and publicising activities (including shortening, summarising, inserting other elements (such as meta-data, legends, other graphic, visual, audio or text elements), extracting parts (e.g. audio or video files), dividing into parts, use in a compilation);

(d) translation;

(e) giving access in response to individual requests under Regulation No 1049/200127, without the right to reproduce or exploit;

(f) storage in paper, electronic or other form;

(g) archiving, in line with applicable document-management rules, and

(h) the right to authorise third parties to act on its behalf or sub-license the modes of use set out in Points (b), (c), (d) and (f) to third parties if needed for the communication and publicising activities of the Agency or the Commission.

In order to complete this set of information's provided in a resumed way in this report, the Project partners are encouraged to consult the following key documents and online sources for the definition of various terms and description of various procedures and processes as well as the respective roles and responsibilities of each party:

- **The Athena Grant Agreement including: Annex 1 – Description of the Action, in particular Subsection 3, o Rights and Obligations related to results, description of Article 29 – Dissemination of Results – Open Access – Visibility of EU Funding, as well as Article 38 — Promoting the action — Visibility of EU funding, from the same section**
- **European IPR Helpdesk's Fact Sheet "The Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results in Horizon 2020"**

(https://www.iprhelphdesk.eu/sites/default/files/newsdocuments/FS-Plan-for-the-exploitation-anddissemination-of-results_1.pdf).

Partners can refer to the following links for downloading support material:

- I. **The EU emblem:** https://europa.eu/european-union/about-eu/symbols/flag_en
- II. **Guidelines on the use of the EU emblem:**
https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/use-emblem_en.pdf
- III. **Graphical rules:** <http://publications.europa.eu/code/en/en-5000100.htm>

Partners should keep track of all their dissemination and exploitation activities, all of which should be reported by each partner at EC reporting stages. Partners are required to report (ongoing) any publication and dissemination activities on the Research Participant Portal.

The H2020 online manual provides brief descriptions on how to complete your tasks, guidance notes, templates, user manuals of the relevant tools and frequently asked questions. The manual is available at:
http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/index_en.htm

3 IMPLEMENTATION

3.1 Target Groups & Tools

According to the orientations of the GA the WP7 is expected to develop specific communication measures and tools to be implemented during the ATHENA project. These communication measures and tools should deliver the key messages outlining the project's objectives and results and enhance its visibility to different groups of stakeholders: centres for women's studies and research, academic and educational institutions, NGOs – especially women's organisations, EU institutions, political decision-makers (EU, regional and local levels), professional associations, etc.

These specific communication measures and tools will be developed, available and implemented during the ATHENA project to deliver the key messages outlining the project's objectives and results and enhance its visibility to different groups of stakeholders.

They include, for example, centres for women's studies and research, academic and educational institutions, NGOs – especially women's organisations, EU institutions, political decision-makers (EU, regional and local levels), professional associations, etc, as you can also consult in Table 1.

The definition of the target audience and the objective context for each stakeholder will encompass the visual identity of the project as well as a communication toolkit including a logotype, leaflet, poster and roll-up banner, templates (PPT, Word), newsletters and press releases. All the graphic image is to be defined by a graphic company to be subcontracted by the FRCT, as all the content is to be fed by FRCT, with the collaboration and inputs from the Athena partners, namely translations in their mother tongue. Through this process WP7 starts with the roadmap settled by the D7.1, the project outcomes and thus the results of the implementation of the GEPs in partner institutions will be disseminated to a wide community, through communication tools described in Table 1, ensuring the **sustainability** of initiated actions after the project life cycle. The dissemination and communication strategy developed within WP7 is the basis to contribute to a maximization of the impact of ATHENA's project.

Among the relevant stakeholders identified by partners, three are the key target groups that need to be reached through communication activities: On one hand, it is fundamental that partner organisations' staff and **students are aware of project results and take part in its activities to ensure systemic changes at institutional level**; on the other hand, policy makers and other research organisations in **both project countries and in other EU Member States must be involved in ATHENA**. Activities planned under

WP6 and WP7 have been foreseen in order to facilitate the **engagement of these groups**, as described in the table below:

Target audience	Dissemination/Communication main method/vehicle*	Reasons
Athena partners	E-mails; One-on-One; Reports; Briefings	Direct contacts; common guidelines and commitments
Universities/ Institutions/ Research Organizations	Newsletters; Reports; Posters; Scientific publications; Workshops; Web-seminars; Conferences; Website	Information more related to knowledge development (receive and contribute)
Students/Youth	Social Media; Videos; Posters; Web-conferencies;	A digitally connected generation more open to digital contents
Media	Press releases; briefings; Conferences; posters; social media posts; website; videos	Information that is oriented to the main stream interest
Policy Makers	Website; Social media; Reports; Booklets	A mix of technical information and digitally accessible information, targeting wider audiences and general/transversal interests
Gender Organizations	Reports; Briefings; Emails; Newsletters; Workshops; Conferences; Scientific Publications	Related to the share and exchange of technical and scientific gender information
EURAXESS network	Website; Social media; Reports; Newsletter; Reports; Briefings; web seminars	Network adjustable, digital, with scientific and technical information

Table 1: Identify the range of different dissemination media to engage particular target audiences.

*The following list offers a set of different types of dissemination & communication[XXX] to be considered:

Mailing lists	Newsletters	Briefings	Conferences
E-mails	Reports	Workshops	Web seminars
Booklets	Posters	Athena Website	Flyers
Press releases	Social Media posts	One-to-one	Scientific publications
Website	Videos	Non scientific publication	Organization of local events

Table 2. Tools for dissemination and communication to be used in Athena project

- **Athena's Partners**

Visual identity, along with website, platform and social media, will play a key role in raising awareness of the project at organisational level. Staff and students will be invited to join and interact on the e- Platform that will be developed under WP6. Press releases, deliverables and other key results of the project such as the Toolbox and the Gender Audit will be disseminated among partners' research and teaching staff and, whenever possible, presented in relevant conferences and other events organised within partners' institutions.

- **Universities/ Institutions/ Research Organizations**

Other research organizations will be contacted and informed about ATHENA improvements and outputs, including centers for women's studies and research. This will be mainly achieved by exploiting the networks identified in Table 3 by the Athena's partners and the additional ones that will be integrated in the stakeholder database. The activities will be directed at several levels, from: Higher and middle management; HR professional; Professor and researchers; and Administrative staff

- **Students/Youth**

The change starts in the young generations and by following that idea the Athena communication and dissemination will have particular attention to this target public. They will be involved at several levels in the project, namely as volunteers in some actions, as well as being called to contribute to several deliverables of the project. In the WP7 context the students will be asked to vote on the logo, in the context of an open contest promoted in the ATHENA's partners Universities. Students and professors will be asked to provide vote on a logo option. This will help raise awareness, as well as engage them in the project activities awareness since the very beginning and along the project actions.

- **Media**

Starting from the very beginning of the project partners will publish at least 20 press releases -two per partner that will be disseminated through different media at regional and/or national level.

- **Policy makers**

Policy makers will be informed about project results during local events organized in each RPO and RFO of the ATHENA project and they will be invited to attend the final conference. In addition, an ad hoc webinar for policy makers is foreseen in WP6, and it will be focused specifically on policies supporting strategies and gender equality

promotion under structural funds. Publications, media dissemination, newsletters, press releases and other direct mailings will be also exploited as means to reach relevant national, regional and local authorities.

- **Gender organizations**

Gender organizations should be, in one hand, the long “arm” of Athena, to reach a larger audience and in the other hand it can also support the project with knowhow and contribute with valued information that may be used in the communication as well as in other WP’s of the project, making use of the network, resources and knowledge already existent on gender equality promotion to be used as the base of work of the project actions.

- **EURAXESS network**

ATHENA will establish synergies with the EURAXESS network, other EU funded projects as well as with the ERA initiative and network. Namely, synergies and partnership with EURAXESS TOP III project (“Making European research careers more attractive by developing new services and enhancing the current services of the EURAXESS network”) are foreseeing along the project. For instance, one or more partners of the EURAXESS TOP III project will be invited to attend Athena’s webinar, as well as to join the e-platform (WP6) and possibly, to participate as external experts in one of the three mutual learning events organised under WP3. Local events in project countries will be also planned to disseminate project results.

3.2 Level of impact

Image 2. Link between different levels of communication and dissemination regarding the overall Plan for Athena WP

These target groups should be engaged under 5 main target impacts, as in the image above, through: Commitment; Support and favorability; Awareness; Understanding; Involvement.

Awareness: This is the first stage of contact at a communication level, where we approach the public audience to create a conscience that was not there before or at least not clear enough regarding the gender inequality issue in science and research. This is also the first opportunity to reach a wider audience.

Support and Favorability: This kind of impact led us to expand our network of communication and dissemination, as the public audience is supporting and favorable of our message will also disseminate and communicate the actions that we organize within the project, as well as actively participate in the actions offered by the project (events; newsletter enrollment; interviews; pools..), with a positive effect to the participation in the projects WP's activities.

Understanding: The success of this strategy of dissemination and communication will only be achievable and successful if, from the outset, there is an understanding of exactly what it is that Athena want to attain and why. That is why this is an important

point to share the vision and common understanding of what the project has to offer and its relevance.

Commitment: At this stage we promote the participation but also the commitment of the target audience with the goals of the project, as it was there own. This is a deeper level of engagement were the committed implement, support implementation and promote the implementation, not only in other institutions as well as their own. It's an identification with the project values and goals towards an active and committed participation.

Involvement: is the act or process of taking part in something. This level of interaction is active and present, with an active participation in the project activities. As well as the desire to contribute with ideas and be present in the events, initiatives, and be up-to-date with the project activities. This is especially important in the field of the digital tools, as social media and website, as well as events participation.

We measure the impact at these different levels according to the following actions: Participation in events; Sharing info of the project in the social media or traditional media (newspapers; television; radio); number of followers in social media; number of visits to Athena's website; number of publications/shares in the social media; availability to grant interviews to Athena partners; other media actions on gender linked to the project. As other examples described in the table below

On the following table 3 you will find the description in details regarding the target actors as well as the link with Workpackages and main tools of dissemination identified for each, as well as the type/impact/goal of message. This will have also the involvement of the WP's leaders, as well as the vision of the AT partners.

Targets, Timescales and Criteria for Success						
Goal of the communication/ dissemination	Target Group(s)	Target	WP	Tasks	Activities/tools	Criteria for Success
Awareness	Athena partners	Staff directly and indirectly in the project	WP3	T3.2; T3.3; T3.4;T7.3	Trainings, mutual learning workshops; social media	Level of engaging in all the process of dissemination and communication and participation in trainings
	Universities/Research Institutions	Professors/ Researchers	WP3; WP5; WP6; WP7	T3.2; T3.3; T5.1;T6.1; T7.3	Trainings; flyers and brochures;	Participation in events; sharing info of the project; followers in social media; visits to website
		Senior managers (rectors and vice rectors), middle managers, HR staff, administrative staff,	WP3; WP4; WP5; WP6; WP7	T3.2; T3.3;T4.1; T4.3; T5.1;T6.2; T7.2; T7.3	Trainings; flyers and brochures	Participation in events/Trainings; sharing in social media of info on the project and events
		Students	WP6; WP7	T7.2; T7.3; T6.2	Social media posts; flyers and brochures	Participation in events; sharing info of the project; follows in social media; visits to website
	Media	Journalist; scientific publications	WP7	T7.3	Press releases; posts in social media	Number of publications/shares; interviews to Athena partners/partner organizations; other media actions on gender linked to the project
	Policy Makers	Local; Regional and National level	WP3; WP6; WP7	T7.3, T6.1, T6.4	Emails; social media posts	Number of followers in the social media, participation in initiatives; emails addressed with questions to Athena partners

	Gender Organizations	Experts	WP6;WP7	T6.2; T7.3	Events; social media and website	
Support and Favorability	Universities/Research Institutions	Professors/ Researchers	WP2; WP3; WP5; WP6	T2.3.1; T2.3.2; T3.2; T3.3 T6.2, T6.5 ; T5.2	Interviews; survey; Storytelling; contribute in populating the module with the GEPs data; trainings; contribute in populating the module with the GEPs data	Number of references of Athena in scientific papers; Participation in events; Number of voluntary contributions to Athena work
		Internal staff	WP2	T2.3 (T2.3.1)	Interviews; survey	Participation in the surveys and interviews
		Students	WP6; WP7	T6.2; T7.3	Local events; publications in social media	Number of follow in the social media, participation in initiatives; emails addressed with questions to Athena partners
		HR professional	WP2; WP3	T2.3 (T2.3.1); T3.2; T3.3; T5.2	Surveys; Focus groups; contribute in populating the module with the GEPs data	New directives and orientation's implemented; participation in the surveys;
	Media	Journalist; scientific publications	WP6; WP7	T6.2; T7.3	Local events; publications in social media	Number of publications about Athena/or that mention Athena; requests for interviews; media coverage (presence) of Athena events;
	EURAXESS network	R&I Stakeholders	WP7	T7.3	Website; social media	Dissemination of the project results; Communication of gender issues, linked to Athena
	Policy Makers	Middle/high level policy makers, at a national and regional level	WP6	T6.2; T6.3	Events; ATHENA e-Platform for Action	Publication of opinion articles; participation in Athena events and promotion of discussion and contribution in Athena Platform
	Gender Organizations	R&I Stakeholders	WP6; WP7	T6.3; T7.4	ATHENA e-Platform for Action; Scientific publications	Dissemination of the project results; Number of publications about Athena

						(events; trainings; scientific papers..);
Understanding	Athena partners	Staff directly and indirectly in the project	WP3; WP4; WP5	T3.2; T3.3; T3.4; T4.1; T4.3; T5.2; T7.5	Mutual learning events; trainings; social media; website; newsletter; Participation and organisation of events and connection/synergies with similar initiatives; contribute in populating the module with the GEPs data; GEPs best practice analysis; ATHENA toolbox for customized GEPs	Direct participation in activities, use of materials and tools developed by the project such as the online trainings and webinars and other training materials or guidelines
	University/Research Institutions	Professors	WP3; WP4; WP6;	T3.1; T3.2; T3.3; T3.4; T4.3; T6.2; T6.3; T7.3	Mutual learning; Gender Equality Plans Implementation (GEPI) Committees; Trainings events; trainings; social media; website; newsletter	Direct participation in activities, use of materials and tools developed by the project such as the online trainings and webinars and other training materials or guidelines;
		Researchers	WP3; WP4; WP6; WP7	T3.1; T3.2; T3.3; T3.4; T4.3 T6.2; T6.3, T6.4; T7.3;	Mutual learning; Gender Equality Plans Implementation (GEPI) Committees; Trainings events; trainings; social media; website; newsletter	Direct participation in activities, use of materials and tools developed by the project such as the online trainings and webinars and other training materials or guidelines
		HR staff	WP6	T3.1; T3.2; T3.3; T6.3; T7.3	Mutual learning events; Gender Equality Plans Implementation (GEPI) Committees; Trainings; social media	Direct participation in activities; Use of materials and tools developed by the project such as the online trainings and webinars and other training materials; participation

		Students	WP6; WP7	T3.1; T3.2; T3.3; T6.3; T7.3	Mutual learning events; Gender Equality Plans Implementation (GEPI) Committees; Trainings; social media	Direct participation in activities; re-shares; use of Athena hashtags (specific of the project)
		Middle and High level management (Rector; Vice-rectors)	WP3; WP4; WP6; WP7	T3.2; T3.3; T3.4; T4.3 T6.2; T6.3, T6.4; T7.3;	Mutual learning events; trainings; website; newsletter	Direct participation in activities of training/mutual learning; visits to the website; enroll in website
	Media	Journalist; scientific publications	WP6; WP7	T6.3; T7.3	Press releases; social media posts; website information/links; newsletter	Publication on newspaper, radio, social media, as well as the use of Athena's hashtags to promote thematic publications/activities/ related to Athena and interviews with partners
	Policy Makers	Middle/high level policy makers, at a national and regional level	WP6	T6.3	ATHENA e-Platform for Action;	Participation in the interactive forum of the ATHENA e-Platform for Action
Involvement	Athena partners	Staff directly and indirectly in the project	WP2; WP3; WP7	T2.2; T2.4; T3.2; T3.3; T7.5	Report contributions; Participation and organisation of events and connection/synergies with similar initiatives	Level of engagement in all the process of dissemination and communication either is providing information and also promoting or seeking actively participation in events to present Athena project
	Universities/Research Institutions	Professors/ Researchers	WP2; WP3; WP7; WP6	T2.2; T3.1; T3.2; T3.3; T7.5; T7.6; T6.1	Training; social media posts; events; focus groups; GEPI Committee Chairs,	Participation in trainings and events; engaging in the exchanges of ideas/articles on the platform and focus groups
		Internal staff	WP3; WP7	T3.1; T3.2; T3.3 T7.3; T7.6	Training; Final international conference; social network	Participation in trainings and events, namely IN the final conference; follow the social networks of Athena

		Students	WP2; WP7	T2.2 T7.1; T7.3; T7.4; T7.6	Open competition; online posts; newsletter; focus group; social network	Level of participation in Athena events (call to choose the logo, for example and other online campaigns); follow the social networks of Athena and use Athena's hashtags
		HR professional	WP3; WP7	T3.1; T3.2; T7.6	Training; newsletter; social network	Number of emails received with requests of information requirements; integration of new gender orientations in managing and selecting HR; participation in the trainings; follow Athena's social network
	EURAXESS network	R&I Stakeholders	WP6; WP7	T6.3;T6.5; T7.3; T7.4; T7.5; T7.6	Webseminars; workshops; final international conference	Invitations to participate in activities; number of shares of Athena events and achievements in social network/email/website; participate in the final international conference
	Policy makers	Middle/high level policy makers, at a national and regional level	WP6; WP7	T6.4; T6.5; T7.5; T7.6	Webseminars; workshops; final international conference; social media; final international conference	Direct participation in Athena's activities; share posts of the project; follow the social networks of the project; participate in the final international conference
	Gender Organizations	Experts	WP6; WP7	T6.3; T7.5; T7.6	Webseminars; workshops; final international conference; social media; final international conference	Invitations to participate in activities; follow the projects social networks and be active, as the number of shares of Athena posts (events and achievements) in social network/email/website; participate in the final international conference

Commitment	Athena partners	Staff directly and indirectly in the project	WP2; WP3; WP7	T2.1; T2.2; T2.4; T3.1; T3.2; T4.4; T4.5; T7.3;T7.4;T7.5;T7.6;	Social Media; Website; Newsletter; Training; final international conference; local events; Tool kits; Bilateral discussions; Approval and implementation of GEPs	Participation in the Athena’s diagnostic; trainings, events; bilateral discussions
	Universities/Institutions	Professors	WP2; WP3; WP4; WP7	T2.1; T2.2; T2.4; T3.1; T3.2; T4.3; T7.4	Training; Workshop; drafting GEPs and development of GEP; Tool kits; Bilateral discussions; Scientific articles	Participation in the trainings; providing scientific articles on the issues promoted by Athena; Be speakers/trainer, in a volunteer base in Athena initiatives; use Athena’s results to publish Scientific articles
		Researchers	WP2; WP3; WP4; WP7	T2.1; T2.2; T2.4; T3.1; T3.2; T4.3; T7.4	Training; Workshop; drafting GEPs and development of GEP; Tool kits; Bilateral discussions ; Scientific articles	Participation in the trainings; providing scientific articles on the issues promoted by Athena; Be speakers/trainer, in a volunteer base in Athena initiatives; use Athena’s results to publish Scientific articles
		Internal staff	WP3; WP4	T3.1; T3.2; T4.3	Training; Workshop; drafting GEPs and development of GEP	Participation in the trainings/workshops
		HR Experts	WP3; WP4; WP7	T3.1; T3.2; T4.3; T7.6	Training; Workshop; ATHENA toolbox for customized GEPs; participation final international conference (online or in person)	Integrate guidelines in the recruitment process; Disseminate the Athena guidelines and other outputs of the project.
		Middle and High level management (Rector; Vice-rectors)	WP4; WP7	T4.4; T4.5; T7.6	Training; Workshop; participation final international conference (online or in person);	Be speakers/trainer, in a volunteer base in Athena initiatives; visits to the Athena website;

					website; documents of the project; GEP; Final international conference	downloads of the Athena project documents; implementation of the tailored GEPs, participation in discussions for GEP implementation
	Research Organization	Researchers	WP4; WP7	T4.4; T4.5; T7.4	GEPs and project documents; scientific articles	Promotion of Athena results and events, participation in discussions for GEP implementation
	EURAXESS network	R&I Stakeholders	WP4; WP7	T4.3; T7.6	GEPs and project documents; Final international conference	Promotion of Athena results and events, as well as promoting the implementation of the tailored GEPs and the final international conference
	Policy makers	Middle/high level policy makers, at a national and regional level	WP4; WP7	T4.5; T7.6	GEPs and project documents; Final international conference	Participate, either as participant, host or speaker in Athena's project; promote the GEP's implementation (shares of Athena's results and articles)
	Media	Journalist; scientific publications	WP4; W7	T4.5; T7.6	Press releases; Athena's website	Promotion of GEP's implementation and dissemination of Athena's events and outcomes

Table 3: Definition the type of goal and link it to your target audience, within the WP's tasks during the Athena project life

3.3 Success - monitoring and evaluation

An effective dissemination strategy will only continue to be effective if you define specific targets, these will allow us to evaluate and determine either it needs to be readjusted or not, as an evolving and constant developing process.

The environment around you will change during the lifecycle of Athena project and the contexts within which your target audience are working will also follow that change. This means we need to put in place suitable mechanisms for reviewing our progress and the extent to which our dissemination strategy is meeting your objectives. The measures of success, as we will also do with the follow up tables, as in table 3 and table 4, to register dissemination and communication process will allow us to measure the level of impact and engagement we are reaching. As for the number of shares, likes, follow that we will have in the social media, as well as the number of enrollments in the newsletter, number of participants in the Athena events, etc.

To be able to define the Key performance indicators (KPIs), as monitoring points of the D&C activities, will support the measurement of successful D&C activities in the Athena project. The communication and dissemination WP defines the following KPIs:

Communication activity/results	Indicator	Targets
Webinars	Number of webinars, participants and shares of the event	2 webinars organized; at least 25 participants per webinar (taking in to account that we have organizations of different sizes in the project); At least 20 shares per webinar in the social media
Production of scientific publications	Number produced; number accepted	At least 1 produced per partners during the project lifetime
Non scientific publications	Number produced and published (press releases; opinion articles, for example)	At least 1 produced per partners during the project lifetime (8 in total)
Posters/papers at scientific conferences	Number	At least 1 per partner
Appearance on EC webpage (CORDIS, Research and Innovation webpage, etc)	Number	At least 20
Informative printable material: posters, brochures, project factsheet	Number	At least 100 per country (as it will be also available online for download).
Videos	Number of videos produced; Number of views and shares;	At least 1 video per partner (8 in total); At least 200 views per video; At least 20 shares per video
Newsletters	Number of newsletters, Number of subscriptions	6 newsletters; at least 500 subscribers until month 48; at

	Number of downloads (in the website)	least 20 downloads per newsletter
Social network campaign (Twitter, Facebook, Youtube and Instagram), partner websites	Number of posts, number of fans / members achieved/shares	At least 1 post per week on social media - in Twitter, Instagram and Facebook; ATHENA minimum number of follower: - Facebook: 2000 followers; - Instagram: 1500 followers; - Twitter: 2500 followers. At least 100 shares per account.
Participation in the media (TV, radio)	Number of appearances	2 appearances per country
Participation in relevant events	Number of Conferences and other events attended, number of project presentations	Attending at least 5 technical conferences and/or seminars and/or fairs for dissemination purposes, per partner
Press releases	Number of press releases	Overall 20 press releases, at least 1 per partners
Participation in relevant events	Number of participations	Participation on at least 2 relevant international conferences and one at a national/regional level
Organization of local events	Number of events and participants	Organization least 2 local events per partners with a minimum of 20 participants in each event

Table 4 The listing of KPI's of the Athena D&C Strategy activities

3.4 Messages

To achieve the expected impact, the WP7 follows a multi-actor approach (as described in table 3), through which it's essential to define and convey a clear message be successful in the WP7 actions. The message has to be supported by the values that the project wants to represent and that the multi-stakeholders can identify with.

The values linked with the objective of Athena's project are based on 3 main pillars: Equality; Justice; Conscience. These pillars should be transversal to all the communication messages, inherent to the message we want to convey, in order to not focus solely on the feminist cause, as this is a human rights matter. Through a more inclusive message, we reach a wider spectrum, as message towards the respect of human rights, linked with the equality of opportunities/recognition/conditions/justice, independently to the gender.

Image 3 The pillars for Athena message, as guiding values to construct the Athena's messages.

Conscience is the stage of learning that allows the several stakeholders to have scientific information produced and disseminated by Athena to identify the lack of justice and equality, as well as solutions - the measures/guidelines that the project presents and use these three pillars as values align with their organizations in order to implement the GEP's. The messages should take in to consideration the following context in order to build the narrative of communication for a wide aim and potential impact:

- **At partner level:**

In each partner RPO and RFO representatives of the four target groups considered in ATHENA – high and middle management, HR professionals, professors and researchers and administrative staff, together with voluntary students – will be mobilised and will take part in project activities directly. In addition, other staff and students of partner institutions will be informed about project results and involved in some of the dissemination and exploitation activities foreseen.

- **At regional, country level**

Local, regional, national and European stakeholders -including national, regional and local policy makers, NGOs, professional orders, European and International institutions - will be contacted and invited to events organised by project partners with the aim of disseminating project achievements, highlighting positive changes observed in the partner organisations and inspiring them to follow the same approach. ATHENA partners have to identify the key groups of stakeholders that need to be reached and involved in the project that are part of their local/national Research Performing Organisations including Universities, Research Funding Organisations, Professional orders, policy-makers, relevant Ministries and regional and local authorities, European Umbrella's organisations related to gender and research, European and International institutions. Stakeholders identification and engagement through the organization of two local events per partner aiming at sharing project results and achievements for potential transfer of the gender equality actions developed and implemented in WP4. Local events in project countries will be also organised to present project results, and budget has been allocated for this purpose.

- **Transversal and wider spectrum of stakeholders**

Increase the visibility and impact of the project both at local, national, European and international level (specially neighboring countries). The dissemination activities will aim at sharing and promoting the progress and achievements of the project, as well as at facilitating the participation of relevant stakeholders. The key target groups of the dissemination activities include therefore both direct and indirect beneficiaries of the project. The Workpackage, together with the communication and dissemination activities in WP7, will make the project results replicable. The project will have a wider impact by implementing synergies with the EURAXESS network, other EU funded projects as well as with the ERA initiative and network.

3.5 Main milestones

The Athena project has eleven milestones related to the internal management and strategy of the project and outcomes related to the development of work. These are milestones that start in month 2 of the project and go along the project life up until month 48. The main outcomes are plans; reports; indicators; data; strategy and newsletters. Each milestone may be foreseen as an opportunity to communicate to the stakeholders the goals and actions that the project has achieved, therefore with dissemination interest, in order to engage, inform and involve the target public of the project.

Therefore it's important that the lead beneficiaries of the milestones engage with the WP7 leader in order to determine what kind and what message, target public and means should be used to disseminate the milestone outcome – the results in the “means of verification”.

Milestone number	Milestone Title	Lead Beneficiary	Due date	Means of verification
MS1	Data Management Plan	1 - CE	2	Data Management Plan
MS2	Management and Coordination Plan	1 - CE	3	After the kick-off meeting, a management and coordination Plan will be drafted identifying the person responsible for each task and the responsibilities inside the management bodies of the consortium
MS3	Common database for gender equality audit	7 - UVSK SAV	12	Indicators and data to be collected by RPOs and RFOs will be identified and communicated to project partners within this report
MS4	Members of GEPI committees identified	1 - CE	7	List of members of GEPI committees
MS5	Gender Training for GEPI Committees completed	1-CE	12	Report of the trainings activities
MS6	Training activities for RPO's and RFO's completed	1 - CE	24	Report of training activities
MS7	GEPs approved	1 - CE	17	GEPs texts approved
MS8	GEPs monitoring and evaluation system	3 - UJK	16	Monitoring and evaluation system working
MS9	Populating GEPVISION	6 - CNR	48	On-line data of GEPs implemented, allowing RPOs and RFOs to constantly and effectively monitoring progresses during GEPs implementation.
MS10	Dissemination and communication strategy	10 - FRCT	3	The dissemination and communication strategy developed within WP7 will be

				the basis for maximizing the impact of ATHENA
MS11	Newsletter	10 - FRCT	8	The project newsletters will be developed and translated into all the languages of the project partners

Table 5 Milestones on Athena project

Messages will support the communication of each sub-objective of the project and are interconnected with the different levels of communication with stakeholders, on figure 1, as well as they have objective of:

1. **Review:** To assess current gender situation in the RPOs and RFOs in terms of Gender Plans, as well as verify and identify gender actions being implemented
2. **Reflect:** To create an evidence base of best practices/guidelines and lessons learned from sister project, in order to identify advantages, obstacles and capability gaps in current EU RPOs and RFOs, as well in Euroaxes networks
3. **Recommend:** To complement and adjust existing capacities, policies, and initiatives for gender discrimination prevention, through an inclusive policy practices, dialogue and the development of policy recommendations.

3.6 Synergies

The WP7, as well as its deliverables and tasks previews work based on partnership and the principles of reciprocity and work-sharing, aimed at combining propulsive synergies and providing a frame for communication and dialogue. These synergies will maximize the result of the WP7 goals and results, by implementing its actions as a transversal WP along the project, adjusted to each country's characteristics and needs, as well as integrating each partners view and perspective. All project partners are in charge of providing information for the publication of news in the website and social media.

Between WP's

The results the project will come out with and the developed GEPs will be disseminated across Europe to ensure that other research organisations start to implement gender equality plans. This will be achieved by carrying out activities the will result of synergies between WP6 and WP7, tailored to the different groups of stakeholders that need to be informed about ATHENA achievements, in particular other RPOs and RFOs and EU, national, regional and local policy-makers. These activities will entail for instance the launch of a web-based community platform built around the work of the project and that will include a database/compendium of women's researchers at EU level to make women's contributions visible, webinars, publications, organisation of dissemination events at local and European level, recording of video interviews with research organizations representing best practices.

Task 7.4 Open Source Scientific Publications, M6-M48: With regard to publications, FRCT together with CNR will identify the most relevant journals and conferences, providing guidelines to researchers and other stakeholders, in order to publish the article produced during the project implementation such as new data on the status of Gender Equality in EU Eastern countries and European Islands (related to D2.2), the Toolbox for transforming the institutional culture in terms of gender aspects (related to D4.3) and the GEPs impact report (related to D5.4).

WP1 - Management and coordination (CE)

This WP will support and complement the WP7 as it will ensure communication among partners and coordination of all activities and will be the interface among the project and the EC.

WP2 - Gender Equality Audit and assessment of procedures and practices at organisational and national level (UVSK SAV)

The WP2 will be the starting point to provide a strong base of quantitative and qualitative information that will sustain and support the message to be communicated by the WP7 regarding the project relevance, message and goals. The data collected in WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5 will be available for defined stakeholders by the WP2, as policy makers but also for researchers and communicated to the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) to support their studies and analysis. The Consortium Agreement and the Data Management Plan will indicate that beneficiaries will give each other access, on a royalty free basis, to background needed to implement their own tasks under the action. The beneficiaries will also give each other access to results needed for implementing their own tasks during the implementation stage of the project.

The WP7 can be a good support to disseminate the surveys and interviews to be carried by the T2.3, these surveys will be available, namely, online through the project website. Documents, that are public, such as the Common database for gender equality audit, as well as the Report on national status in gender equality in each partner country, as well as Gender equality reports will give the communication leader the information to sustain the message to be delivered to the stakeholders by the project. Several press releases, as well as post can be developed based on these information's provided by the WP2 leader.

WP3 - Capacity building for systemic institutional change (CE)

The actions developed under the WP3 will benefit and have a maximized impact if it uses the full advantages offered by the D&C activities/tools in the WP7. In WP3 partner organisations' staff will be involved in two gender training programmes for representatives of the ATHENA GEPI Committees and for the internal staff, respectively. The training for the GEPI committees will be composed of two online trainings and one face-to-face training. They will be delivered in the national languages of ATHENA countries. The second training devoted to the internal staff will be composed of five modules and will be focused on different topics according to the individual needs of each organisation – the outcome and dissemination of this activity will be important to disseminate the project activities as well as the goals and relevance of these trainings trough the channels provided by WP7, namely the newsletters, the website and e-platform and social networks.

WP4 - GEPS Development and implementation (CE)

This WP goal is focused on the GEP's creation, namely the toolbox of recommendations (T4.3) and the approval and implementation of the tailored GEPs (T4.5). The WP7 will be a fundamental tool to promote and disseminate this toolbox that will allow an adequate creation and implementation of GEP's. The Athena toolkit will be published in the project's website and e-platform and will be promoted in the social networks, as well as integrated as a project outcome in the newsletter and booklet. A good dissemination will be an essential part of the process to ensure a good communication with the stakeholders of the WP4 work.

The approval of the GEPs (T4.5) will be a relevant and key milestone of ATHENA. Once the GEPs are approved, they will be published on the organisations' and the project's website and related social networks. They will be also disseminated through the ATHENA newsletter and each project beneficiary will issue a press release on the issue.

WP5 - Monitoring and evaluation (CNR)

This WP is focused on the monitoring progresses during the Athena's project regarding the GEP's implementation. The link with the WP7 will be essential ultimately in the D5.5 with the promotion of the report that will be developed and submitted to peer review for publication. The WP7 will orient and assist on regards of the publication as well as the promotion of the data outcomes from this WP's using tools that allow stakeholders to follow-up the process of the Athena's work, as social networks, Athena's website, as well as other sister projects website, and supporting organizations websites, as also through flyers and booklets produced in the context of the project.

WP6 - Sustainability strategy to ensure replication of GEPs and project results (URAK)

Guidelines on how engaging relevant stakeholders in order to maximize impact of project findings and to identify multipliers to build sustainability of the GEPs will be provided. In this sense, in WP6 a stakeholder database, providing details of individuals, groups, organisations and networks that might act as 'multipliers' taking either or both project outcomes and the GEPs to wider constituencies, will be produced in WP6 and it will be periodically updated. Partners have already performed a stakeholder analysis at proposal stage, identifying networks/associations they are part of which will be engaged in the project. In addition to those, a further analysis will be performed to identify additional organisations not only in project countries but also beyond. Last but not least, the contacts with the panel of identified gender experts will serve as a channel to reach stakeholders at a higher level. This set of stakeholders and channels identified by this

WP will contribute positively to increase the range of dissemination and communication of WP7.

The Task 6.2 dedicated to “Stakeholder engagement at local level”, from M16 to M47 of the project, will be implemented in strait link with the WP7, as the WP7 will promote the effects of dissemination, awareness, engaging and support from the general audience and target participants.

Also activities from WP6, as video interviews with research organisations representing best practices that will be recorded to support gender promotion and GEPs implementation in other research organisations, will benefit greatly from dissemination tools offered by the WP7, as website and social media.

The ATHENA e-Platform for Action is the responsibility of WP6 but it’s linked with the Athena’s website that will be developed under the WP7 responsibilities, therefore there will be a close link in the implementation of the ATHENA e-Platform between these two WP’s. This e-Platform will be accessible to the panel of external experts and to all potential stakeholders through a personal username and log-in. This platform will be a tool of dissemination that will support the communication and dissemination activities, making available the results of the project and creating a space for discussion on GEPs development and implementation.

WP8 - Ethics requirements (CE)

This WP’s will provide the WP7 context and adequate handle of information, as it ensures that the communication of the project information is respecting the principals of transparency, privacy and safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subjects/research participants. Therefore the WP7 will be implemented having very present the WP8 orientations.

With other “sister” projects/organizations

ATHENA will ensure contacts and cooperation with relevant similar projects (i.e. funded other the same call or H2020 GERI 2014. GERI 2015, etc.) in order to exchange good practices and create synergies. Previous projects funded under similar thematic/calls and the other project(s) funded under the same call will be contacted in order to exchange information and create synergies. Partners will also promote on the EURAXESS platform the organisations having successfully implemented GEPs in the frame of ATHENA project, therefore attracting skilled researchers and improving the level of their organisation. This process as started at the moment of the Kick off of Athena, with the

good example and knowledge sharing with other H2020 projects under the same thematic, the Spear⁶ and Change projects⁷.

In addition to the project website and platform, synergies with already existing communication channels of the project partners will be put in place in order to multiply the reach-out, maximizing our audience. Direct dissemination of the project's outcomes to the main target audience and relevant stakeholders will be ensured via newsletters and different press- releases disseminated through media at local, regional and national channels, as also mentioned in table 3. Cooperation with sister projects in the communication and dissemination is more than welcome, as it will contribute for maximization of the projects impact.

3.7 Communication tools & activities

Partners will attend conferences, seminars, workshops, etc, at national/European level to present the project in order to promote the Athena project, either by presenting the Athena project in a slot either through informal networking. The participation in these events can be in person or online, depending on future conditions to do so. The Project coordinator (CE) and dissemination communication WP7 leader will ensure opportunities to physically meeting research organisations from other relevant EU funded projects.

Two local events will be organised in RPOs and RFOs during the second part of the project to promote the developed GEPs and the replication of project achievements.

These events have as goals the use of a broad range of tailored tools and actions in order to achieve the following objectives:

- **Raise awareness of the project activities and results;**
- **Disseminate information among relevant stakeholders;**
- **Increase the number of RPOs and RFOs taking up GEPs, addressing gender imbalances and strengthening gender dimension at their organizational level;**
- **Facilitate the internal and external communication of project partners.**

⁶[SPEAR \(gender-spear.eu\)](http://gender-spear.eu)

⁷[The Project | change h2020 \(change-h2020.eu\)](http://The Project | change h2020 (change-h2020.eu))

Image 4. Based on the power point presentation that FRCT made to the Athena’s partners during the project’s Kick off in February 2021

1. Newsletter

In order to keep members and interested persons informed, and to provide regular short updates on the progress and news of the project, a newsletter is sent in the defined periods in the AT GA.

In the period of 48 month of the project life there will be released six newsletters, with the following deadlines and points do be presented:

Newsletter I: September 2021 (M8)

- **Introduction of the project: partners; AB; goals and resume of previewed actions**
- **WP2 resumed outcomes: Task 2.1 and Task 2.2**
- **WP3 resume of Task 3.1**

- **WP7 communication activities – promote the visual identity, Athena’s website and Athena’s social network**
- **Other matters relevant that can be included by common agreement with the WP7 leader, coordinator and WP leaders or/and partners**

Newsletter II: May 2022 (M16)

- **WP2 resumed outcomes of the Task 2.3 and Task 2.4**
- **WP3 resumed outcomes: Task 3.2**
- **WP4 resume of Task 4.1; Task 4.2; Task 4.3; Task 4.4**
- **WP5 resume Task 5.1**
- **WP7 communication activities – promote the events organized by partners or other relevant events in the gender scoop, Athena’s website, Athena’s social network and Antena’s newsletter enrollment**
- **Other matters relevant that can be included by common agreement with the WP7 leader, coordinator and WP leaders or/and partners**

Newsletter III: January 2023 (M24)

- **WP1 resumed outcomes of Task 1.4 (AB)**
- **WP3 resumed outcomes: Task 3.3**
- **WP4 resume of the point of situation of Task 4.5**
- **WP5 resume of the point of situation of Task 5.3**
- **WP6 resume of the point of situation Task 6.1; Task 6.3 and Task 6.5. Outcomes of the Task 6.2.**

- **WP7 communication activities – promote the events organized by partners or other relevant events in the gender scoop, Athena’s website, Athena’s social network and Antena’s newsletter enrollment**
- **Other matters relevant that can be included by common agreement with the WP7 leader, coordinator and WP leaders or/and partners**

Newsletter IV: January 2024 (M36)

- **WP1 resumed outcomes of Task 1.4 (AB)**
- **WP4 resume of the point of situation of Task 4.5**
- **WP5 resume of the point of situation of Task 5.3**
- **WP6 resume of the point of situation Task 6.1 and Task 6.5. Outcomes of the Task 6.4**
- **WP7 communication activities – promote the events organized by partners or other relevant events in the gender scoop, Athena’s website, Athena’s social network and Antena’s newsletter enrollment**
- **Other matters relevant that can be included by common agreement with the WP7 leader, coordinator and WP leaders or/and partners**

Newsletter V: July 2024 (M42)

- **WP1 resumed outcomes of Task 1.4 (AB)**
- **WP5 resume of the point of situation of Task 5.3**
- **WP6 resume of the point of situation Task 6.1 and Task 6.5.**
- **WP7 communication activities – promote the events organized by partners or other relevant events in the gender scoop, Athena’s website, Athena’s social network and Antena’s newsletter enrollment**

- **Other matters relevant that can be included by common agreement with the WP7 leader, coordinator and WP leaders or/and partners**

Newsletter VI: January 2025 (M48)

- **Resume of the project outcomes, infographic style, with numbers and key words and ideas (data on gender; number of events; interviews, etc.)**
- **Interview with the coordinator in representation of the consortium regarding the overall outcomes of the project;**
- **WP1 Task 4.1 (AB) – thank you open letter to the Athena AB role in the project**
- **WP5 Resumed outcomes of the Task 5.3 and Task 5.4**
- **WP6 Resumed outcomes of the Task 6.1; Task 6.3 and Task 6.5**
- **WP7 Resumed outcomes of Task 7.3; Task 7.4; Task 7.5 and Task 7.6**
- **Other matters relevant that can be included by common agreement with the WP7 leader, coordinator and WP leaders or/and partners**

The newsletter will be stepping stones that will give us the opportunity to show the path that we are building, it's results as well as the project activity and dynamic nature. In this sense, the newsletters are a brief and concise with updates and outcomes presentation, original contents on project activities and on gender topics in research and academia (covered by the point "Other matters relevant that can be included by common agreement"). These six newsletters allow the project to keep in contact with the wider audience regarding the project development and outcomes. It connect and resume the work that the project partners have been developing, according to the timing of the deliverables pinpointed in the timing flow. This will define also the content of the newsletter in a way that the newsletters can reflect the development of work done and present increasingly more and more complete data to the stakeholders, as the result of the project activities.

These newsletters will be available in the website for download and will also be sent directly to our target public, accessible by registration. The newsletter will be written in English and in the partners mother tongue so that it can be directed not only to the international community as well as local, regional national target public. The translation of the newsletter should be made by the Athena partner organization (WP7 responsible per organization), translating in to the most faithful version as possible based on the English version.

The newsletter can be download from the ATHENA website and will be sent my Mail Chimp to the list of enrolled stakeholders.

The WP7 leader encourage partners to disseminate the enrollment by link within ATHENA's organization, as well as partner organizations and other identified stakeholders. This can be done by inserting information on this regard in your organization websites and also by referring to the Athena website and newsletter in every press release or event promotion at a local and national level. The dissemination will be made trough social media and Athena partners website.

2. Social networks

The project will be visible and present in several social media. This digital platform will play a key role in raising awareness of the project at organisational level, especially for young target groups, as students, as well as general society.

Social media pages (Twitter, Facebook, Youtube and Instagram) will be created to make project achievements available to a wider public participation and redirect attention towards the website and the online platform for latest development. These pages will developed under the D4.2 activities.

A project channel on Telegram will also be opened to build a community of interest around the work of the project, and in particular reaching students from partner universities and other European ones.

The social media will be managed by the WP7 leader and count on the inputs given by the WP's leaders as well as the partners. The publications may include national, regional topics that are aligned with the Athena goals.

The social media will be the vehicle to promote the following information:

- **General information regarding the project goals;**

- **Events to be promoted in the context of the project by Athena partners;**
- **Events to be promoted by “sister” projects;**
- **Press releases related to the project activities of relevance to be promoted to the general public (as GA; achievements; activities..);**
- **Celebratory dates aligned with the Athena’s goal, as International Women’s Day (IWD)Womens International day (8th of March); International Day of Women and Girls in Science (11th of February); World Science Day for Peace and Development (10th November) and any other that may be signaled by the partners and that can be coherent to be celebrated in Athena’s social media;**
- **Short interviews with partners and stakeholders that promote the project - to be provided by partners;**
- **Good practices and good examples on GEP’s or Women’s and girls in science – story telling style – to be developed in collaboration with the partners that have proposals;**
- **Photos that can encourage/promote and create conscience regarding gender equality in science/research;**

The frequency of the post should vary depending on the project timeline. Although the social media should be active and interactive enough to engage and have fresh information to offer. Therefore, to make this happen it’s essential that there is a joint work of co-collaboration from the part of Athena’s partners with the WP7 leader. This pro-active and dynamic attitude, on proposing subjects to be posted, is essential to keep the social network active. This constant contact and engagement is especially important from the part of the WP7 responsible person from the AT partner (defined by each partner in M2).

To promote the project more widely trough the social network we recommend the use of hashtags associated with Athena project.

Using a hashtag is a way to mobilize behind an important cause or issue. For example, #EachforEqual and #IWD2021 were used across social media platforms, including LinkedIn, on International Women’s Day. Athena project can also create a hashtag that also shows its connection to the audience interest and reach stakeholders and supporters of the gender cause and the Athena project goals.

The hashtag can help us find our target audience as we use the hashtags they use. This method is especially effective within social media sites like Instagram where users can follow hashtags and see all the posts that use them.

Therefore, we suggest the use following combination of hashtags – at least one general and one specific of the project - when posting regarding Athena in your organizations social network or whenever you want to highlight the project, as in the following table:

General hashtags	#genderequality #womeninscience #womenempowerment #womenrights #humanrightsforall #science #humanity #openscience #openeurope #education #h2020projects #Horizon2020 #HorizonEurope #europeanprojects #workplaceculture #transparency
Athena specific hashtags:	#EUAthenagenderproject #Horizon2020_Athena #Athena_for_equality

Table 6. Hashtags for Athena digital promotion and stakeholders reach

3. Scientific publications

Open access: ATHENA will contribute to increase the indicators OA1-OA6 as ATHENA aims at participating at the H2020 pilot project on open data. The project publications and deliverables will be published on open access repositories. The social media will play an important role in this issue as it will publicly the accessibility to the information created in the context of the project.

The Task 7.4 on “Open Source Scientific Publications” (M6-M48), previews the construction of a common table, with the support and in coordination with the WP6 leader (CNR), identify the most relevant journals and conferences, providing guidelines to researchers and other stakeholders, in order to publish the article produced during the project implementation such as new data on the status of Gender Equality in EU Eastern countries and European Islands (related to D2.2), the Toolbox for transforming

the institutional culture in terms of gender aspects (related to D4.3) and the GEPs impact report (related to D5.4).

Given that ATHENA participates as PILOT in Open Research Data in H2020 (ORDP) an accurate and FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) Data Management Plan (DMP) will be produced at project level. The FAIR Data Management Plan describes in detail the procedure to be followed on handling, collecting, managing, storing, and sharing data within ATHENA. Open Access will be guaranteed by granting “gold” open access to scientific publications, where budget has been envisaged. Also “green” open access will also be an option for the responsible partner if the selected journal allows it. Free publishing option of scientific metadata and datasets produced by the project can be made also through open repositories as Zenodo and OpenAIRE.

The European Commission has now officially launched Open Research Europe⁸, the open access publishing platform for scientific articles that present the results of research funded by Horizon 2020, and soon Horizon Europe and Athena’s partners, as beneficiaries of Horizon 2020, are eligible to publish in this EC platform.

Open Research Europe champions open science principles by immediately publishing articles, followed by transparent, invited and open peer review with the inclusion of all supporting data and materials. The names of the reviewers are open, as well as their reviews, which are also citable. As referred by Jean-Eric PAQUET, Director-General of the European Commission Research department (on March 2021), the “Article-level metrics will continuously track the scientific and social impact of publications. Ultimately, Open Research Europe will give everyone, researchers and citizens alike, free-of-charge access to your latest scientific discoveries”

According to Athena’s GA each beneficiary must ‘disseminate’ its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium), as soon as the project starts.⁹

⁸ [open-research-europe official-launch en.pdf \(europa.eu\)](https://open-research-europe-official-launch-en.pdf(europa.eu))

⁹ This does not change the obligation to protect results in Article 27, the confidentiality obligations in Article 36, the security obligations in Article 37 or the obligations to protect personal data in Article 39, all from the Athena GA and of which still apply.

4. Website

The website will work as a window in which all the interested stakeholders can check on the project results, objectives and latest news, therefore it has to include most of the information that the beneficiaries want to showcase related to the WP results, events promoted by the project as well as highlight studies, reports and scientific articles that represent the project and its spirit.

The website will be divided into three distinct areas:

- I. A private area of the website where to store reports, minutes, documents that will be accessible only to project partners and will act as a supporting tool for partners' daily work.**
- II. A public area accessible to the visitors and users who will find not only relevant and updated information about the project objectives, activities, main documents produced, best practices but also other initiatives and links to gender equality and gender mainstreaming.**
- III. A contact page will be created in order to allow the users to enter in contact with the partners, if they would like to. It will also provide information on the various events and activities implemented during the project as well as the relevant outputs produced within the project, like the gender equality audit in WP2 and a specific section dedicated to each developed GEP.**

The **ATHENA e-Platform for Action** will be accessible to the panel of external experts and to all potential stakeholders through a personal username and log-in. This platform will host the results of the project and will stimulate discussion on GEPs development and implementation, also thanks to the Online Community Manager who will stimulate and facilitate discussions on the platform.

In addition to the project website and platform, synergies with already existing communication channels of the project partners will be put in place in order to multiply the reach-out.

Open access: ATHENA will contribute to increase the indicators OA1-OA6 as ATHENA aims at participating at the H2020 pilot project on open data. The project publications and deliverables will be published on open access repositories. The website, along the social media, will play an important role as it contribute to publicly the accessibility to the information created by the project WP's.

5. Events

Organisation and attendance of dissemination events such as conferences, seminars, workshops and/or other events organised by similar EU funded projects at national and EU level, organisation of a final project conference in Brussels presenting project results are previewed along the project life cycle. Examples of events where ATHENA could be presented are the Gender Summit Europe and the Annual Era Conference. ATHENA will also ensure contacts and cooperation with relevant similar project (i.e. funded other the same call or H2020 GERI 2014, GERI 2015, etc.) in order to exchange good practices and create synergies. The WP7 leader has shared with Athena partners a table (on M2) to be filled in with suggestions/sharing/indications of relevant events regarding Athena's scoop. This share of information will allow each partner to analyze the existing events and select the ones they want to participate, as the budgeted previews such participations/representations.

At least two local events per partner will be organised from M16 (May 2022), at M18 (July 2022) to M46 (January 2025). These will be open public events for interested stakeholders, such as professors, researchers, public authorities, etc. identified in Task 6.1. At least 20 participants for each event will be involved.

The workshops will disseminate the following information:

- 1. Barriers/challenges and the solutions to overcome those encountered during the development of the GEPs and the activities that will be implemented thanks to the adoption of the GEPs;**
- 2. The toolbox and guidelines (M18);**
- 3. Demonstrate how promoting gender equality can unlock research potential, boosting the performance of the organisations and unlocking the research potential (M48).**

The communication and dissemination activities will be mostly focused on the activities promoted in the context of the Task 6.2, dedicated to "Stakeholder engagement at local

level”, from M16 (May 2022) to M47 (December 2025) of the project. The WP6 therefore will be in strait communication with the WP7 for promoting the effects of dissemination, awareness, engaging and support from the general audience and target participants.

The WP7 will have two specific deliverables dedicated to events in D7.4 (M30) and D7.5 (M48), as you can see in image 1 in the list of deliverables.

6. Flyers & booklets

These tools are to be used to disseminate the results of the collected information by the ATHENA partners. The content is therefore to be provided and created with the Athena partners, including information that can contribute to a better knowledge of the project as well as the gender equality in the RPOs and RFOs in Europe. Namely the state of art of the gender equality as well as the solutions to overcome those encountered during the development of the GEPs.

The timeline to release these flyer should discussed with the WP leaders, as it will be aligned with the results/outcomes of the work previewed within the WP’s in the AT project. All the translations to national language will be the responsibility of each partner. The WP7 representatives will decide between themselves, with the facilitation of the WP7 leader, in case several partners share the same language, which will be the fair distribution of translations to be shared and avoid duplication of work. This will require collaboration for a more efficient work.

Booklet template with option of editable text boxes (for translation purposes): color, folding physical version, tri-fold - for A6 size (148x105mm), with digital and print version - combine photos, with infographics and text, about 2000 characters - all the text to be included in the brochure will be proposed by FRCT to be approved and adjusted by the partners, trough it’s WP7 representative(s);

Flyer template: color – A4 Slim or 148 mm Square Half Fold, with info graph and text boxes framed in the images, with option to edit / insert translated text, from an initial English version, to be made available by FRCT.

7. Poster & banner

These graphic materials will be made available to be used as a communication tool. These will be developed and made available in the context of the D7.2 in M5, June 2021.

The poster is to be used as template to adjust to the several events to be promoted by the project, in a printed version, to support the communication before and during an

Athena Event. This will be also used as a digital image to be shared online, not only in Athena website as well as in the social media.

The poster should be used as a versatile communication tool that can be as well used as a back image on online meetings, for example. It will be designed to be used in a very practical and multi-uses.

- **Poster Template** (for sharing in social networks; printing and as a background image in online meetings), version A3 and A2, with format to send to graphic (to be printed by each partner (in the quantity that each partner finds reasonable and aligned with their budget). The text content will be made available by the FRCT and translated in to national languages by each partner, therefore there will the option to insert translated text (editable);

- **Roll-up banner: The advised printing format is 200 x 85 cm. The TFRCT will make available the format for direct sending and printing in graphics, in the English version (editable in national languages);**

The banner is to be used as an image support during events. Each partner should have at least one printed roll up banner to be visible in the stage, so that the photographs of the event can include the project image. Each partner is responsible for the printing of its material, as well as the translation in to its national language.

8. Videos

A series of video interviews with research organisations will be produced within the Athena project. They will be recorded to present best practices related to the gender dimension and gender equality plans in research organisations, which should serve as a source of inspiration for the replication of GEPs and other measures promoting gender equality in other EU research institutions. These videos are the responsibility of other WP, as the WP6, WP3 and WP4, however the engagement with the WP7 to disseminate and communicate the projects results will be essential to reach stakeholders and pass on the message as a project. These videos are a powerful tool to engage the stakeholders and promote its message that is why this is relevant to point out as tools for the project's D&C strategy. It's required close communication with the WP7 leader in order to maximize the impact effect of these videos that require close synergies between WP's.

These tables will allow to have a wider common view of the dissemination process along the project. This will require an engagement and compromise on the part of each partner by collaborating with this share of information. This will also make it easier to make information available for the monitoring and evaluate the partners performance regarding communication and dissemination actions.

4 COVID situation

The implementation of the WP7, as all the project WP's, are constrained to the current global epidemic that has forced many ongoing EU-funded projects to readjust their activities in accordance to local/national/international restrictions. Given the uncertainty on the evolution of the pandemic in the months to come, provisions were already previewed in order to ensure that project reach their goals and that the activities run as smoothly as possible.

Most of the WP7 activities are mostly online and even Task 7.5 “Participation and organisation of events and connection/synergies with similar initiatives”, previewed for July 2021 to January 2025, will be implemented mostly online due to the current situation with the COVID pandemic.

The foreseen activities involving physical interaction and travels (i.e. face-to-face trainings, mutual learning events, project meetings, etc.) are dependable of the shift of the world pandemic situation, and the international, regional and organizational rules according to this. Therefore the Athena partners should seek alternatives to organize events remotely through the use of online platforms and tools such as Zoom, GoToMeeting, Skype, etc. The costs associated to these platforms would be covered by the part of the budget initially foreseen for the physical activities. For any questions related to this issue you should consult the financial coordinator (Consulta Europa).

Activities such as project's organization of specific workshops in other events or conferences is foreseen, with national and regional interest, as well as international events of relevance for the project thematic and goals, as the Gender Summit Europe and the Annual ERA Conference. The participation can either be in person, if the international situation allows it, or else it can be online depending on the evolution of the current world pandemic. The same situation may occur when it comes to the organization of local events. That is why, due to the high level of uncertainty created by this world pandemic that we have to privileged digital and online tools for promotion and engagement with stakeholder and preview necessary adjustments.

5 HORIZON 2020 GUIDELINES

Under Horizon 2020 guidelines for Communication and Dissemination, the dissemination & exploitation of results of activities should engage beneficiaries. As Horizon 2020 is financed by EU citizens, therefore the benefits and the fruits of the research should reach the largest number reach society as a whole.

The Horizon 2020 Dissemination means sharing research results with potential users - peers in the research field, industry, other players and policymakers, etc. By sharing our research results with the rest of the scientific community we fulfil the intent to contribute to the progress of science in general.

The Athena communication Plan will take in to account an follow the guidelines For Your Dissemination and Exploitation Activities from Horizon Europe, as indicated in the GA.

Ownership and access rights.

All projects receiving Horizon 2020 funding are required to make sure that any peer-reviewed journal article they publish is openly accessible, free of charge (article 29.2. Model Grant Agreement). Consider how you will implement this obligation, which is described in more detail in the Open access section, including detailed guidance.

As for open access to research data the Commission is currently running a flexible pilot on open access to research data, which has recently been extended to cover all thematic areas of Horizon 2020, thus realising the Commission's ambition of "open research data per default", but allowing for opt-outs for some datasets, for instance in cases of intellectual property rights (IPR) protection, personal data or national security issues. The pilot applies to research data underlying publications but beneficiaries can also voluntarily make other datasets open. Projects that do not opt-out must develop a data management plan outlining how data is generated, curated and made accessible, within 6 months of starting work. Further guidance is available in the data management section.

6 CONCLUSION

The WP7 is dedicated to dissemination and exploitation of the results achieved throughout the project and through its D&C actions are designed to strengthen the overall impact of project activities. The dissemination strategy will make use of a broad range of tailored tools and actions, in coordination with the several WP's actions, in order to achieve a better awareness of the project activities and results to attain a successful implementation of gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe.

The WP7 will highlight the produced work/information by the Athena partners among relevant stakeholders, in particular RPOs, including Higher Education Institutions and RFOs and also public authorities in charge of education, research and work policies. By disseminating and communicating these information's dimension at their organisational level. The project will aim to implement these plans in the partner organizations but also to serve as an example for replication effect in order to increase the number of RPOs and RFOs taking up GEPs, addressing gender imbalances and strengthening gender

This WP will also work as a facilitator of internal and external communication between project partners.

An important point regarding the C&D activities is the Open Access to Information, since the project deliverables will be openly accessible by organisations from all over Europe with the purpose of making the result available and facilitating its exploitation and access. This is a responsibility as also a greater incentive to be working to and for the EU citizens towards a more informed society, since this project is focused in a change of culture and social perception regarding women in science. Athena project has the opportunity to bring to the citizens eye the science-based conclusions that the WP7 will promote through the different D&C tools. An aligned work with the vision of the Horizon Europe on the EU projects that is to bring the citizens closer to the European Union activities. This allows an easy access to the scientific work by the European citizens, since this is a result of European public financing, in other words, financed by European citizen.

Overall, the project aims at “reaching more than 5,000 relevant organizations”¹⁰, which currently belong to the networks of project partners. Concerning policy-makers, partners have already identified relevant policy-makers at national, regional, and local level. Through the activities foreseen under WP6 and WP7 the project will bring that interest to a further level facilitating the exploitation of the project results in terms of knowledge base creation for policy making and the replication of the ATHENA gender equality plans.

The WP7, through the D7.1, is the starting point of the ATHENA approach that puts in to the light the work developed by each Athena partner towards a common of reducing the gap in Gender Equality in Europe, but firstly in their own regions and countries, by the engagement and compromise of their organizations in implementing Gender Equality Plans. This is even more significant, as an example, when the Athena partners are from countries and regions that are mostly relatively inactive in gender policies and with this project they have a chance to showcase that it's possible to promote and implement institutional change through a participatory and empowering process towards equal rights in where it's more needed.

¹⁰ As stated in the Athena GA, page 152

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